

The Dynamics of the Parish Pastoral Council Members in Ecclesiastical Service

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Abstract: This theological article explores the multifaceted role of the Parish Pastoral Council (PPC) within the ecclesiastical realm, emphasizing its indispensable responsibility in managing, serving, and nurturing the parish community. Grounded in the rich traditions of the Church, the PPC stands as a linchpin for fostering spiritual growth and community cohesion. The study addresses the pressing need to comprehensively understand the theological significance and practical implications of the PPC's role. It deepens into the challenges faced by the council in modern contexts, questioning how it can effectively navigate contemporary dynamics while remaining true to its foundational purpose. Employing a theological lens, this research combines historical analysis, canonical exploration, and case studies to illuminate the PPC's evolution and contemporary challenges. Drawing from primary sources and real-world examples, the article seeks to provide a holistic understanding of the PPC's mission and efficacy in fulfilling its responsibilities. The article concludes by underscoring the PPC's pivotal role as a spiritual shepherd, emphasizing the importance of collaborative leadership, strategic planning, and pastoral care in fulfilling its mandate. It envisions a renewed appreciation for the PPC as a dynamic entity, integral to the vibrancy, service, and spiritual flourishing of the parish community.

INTRODUCTION

An interesting aspect of the pastoral ministry of the Church is the active involvement of laypeople, one form of which is manifested in the Parish Pastoral Council (PPC). PPC officials play a crucial role in strengthening the Church's pastoral activities, given their significant role as representatives of the laity and assistants or partners to the parish priest in managing pastoral activities. They dedicate themselves voluntarily to ensure the smooth functioning of the Church's life. They are involved in various aspects of service, including planning and coordinating Church activities, ensuring the pastoral needs of the faithful are met, and participating in missionary work and various forms of social service. Their participation reflects a spirit of synodality and a great sense of responsibility towards the Church (Wijaya & Ardianto, 2018).

The involvement of laypeople in the Church's pastoral work is crucial because they are the forefront of the Church in society. However, not many Catholics are willing to become

Church officials, either in local or parish circles or as members of the PPC. This phenomenon has various underlying reasons and dynamics. One identifiable factor is the high responsibility associated with the role of Church officials. PPC officials must be ready to sacrifice their time, energy, and resources to fulfill various tasks and responsibilities related to church administration, organizing activities, and even maintaining church facilities (Cahyadi, 2009). This often becomes an additional responsibility to be carried out alongside personal work and other commitments, making it challenging to balance with daily life demands.

Roles in the Church also often require individuals to actively participate in decision-making processes and financial management, which can be complicated and require specific skills. Concerns about these responsibilities can be a barrier for many Catholics, especially if they feel less confident or lack sufficient knowledge in these areas. Furthermore, there is also the factor of time to consider. Modern life is often busy with work, family, and other social activities. Taking on a role as a church official or a member of the parish council requires a significant time commitment. Finding enough time to carry out these duties without sacrificing other aspects of their lives may be challenging (Golparvar & Abedini, 2014).

In addition to these practical factors, some individuals may have uncertainty or concerns about how they will navigate the dynamics of life in the Church. They might worry about conflict or tension within their community if they take on a more active role. Overall, many Catholics may be unwilling to become church officials in their communities or parish council members for various personal, practical, and social reasons (Diaz, 2022). Efforts might be needed to better understand and address these challenges and provide the necessary support to enable active participation in pastoral work.

Therefore, one urgent aspect to consider in efforts to increase lay participation in pastoral ministry is to pay attention to the balance between church service and their personal work. Balancing church service with personal work is a crucial aspect of the lives of active Catholics in church activities (Marbun, 2020). This balance allows individuals to fulfill the demands of church service or spiritual activities while living their daily lives with integrity and effectiveness.

Church service undoubtedly plays a crucial role in meeting the spiritual and social needs of the faithful. The Church becomes a place where they can deepen their faith, receive social support, and participate in activities oriented towards religious values as outlined in the Church's duties (Chen & Habur, 2020). However, church service or spiritual activities often require a significant time and energy commitment. To maintain balance, PPC officials must be able to manage their time wisely so that they can engage in church service without sacrificing their work or other personal responsibilities.

Church service also plays a crucial role in maintaining and strengthening the Church as the Mystical Body of Christ. Individuals actively involved in the church often play roles as leaders, teachers, or drivers in various programs and initiatives (Sanders, 2017). They help maintain the continuity of the church and contribute to the positive development of the community. However, to maintain balance, it is essential for individuals to continue performing

their work and personal responsibilities without compromising the quality of their involvement in the church. Besides the benefits for individuals, this balance also has a positive impact on the church community as a whole. If members can maintain a good balance, they will be more capable of performing their roles with enthusiasm and high dedication. This enriches church service and creates a positive environment for all community members (Dwiatmaja, 2023).

However, maintaining this balance is not an easy task. It requires time management skills, good communication with superiors at work, and support from family and the church community. A PPC member is also required to have a clear understanding of their priorities and the ability to prioritize wisely. Overall, the need for balance between church service and personal work is crucial to meet the spiritual needs of individuals, support pastoral work, and create harmony in daily life (Purwanto, 2012). This is a challenge that needs to be faced with awareness, discipline, and support from various parties to allow PPC members to fulfill their roles in the church effectively while maintaining a balanced and meaningful personal life.

Therefore, this research aims to explore the phenomenon of PPC participation in the Deanery of Malang City, Diocese of Malang, by delving into a deep understanding of the balance between their church service and personal work. The Church, as a religious institution, plays a crucial role in the lives of the community, especially in the city of Malang. Church services are not only places of worship but also centers for spiritual and social activities that influence the lives of people and the surrounding society. As leaders and main drivers in the local church, PPC officials are required to set an example in living a balanced spiritual life with the demands of their work and personal commitments (Omogo, 2019).

In this research, the author will explore the issue of balancing church service with personal work. Church service is not limited to worship alone but also includes various social, educational, and community service activities, and so on. However, amidst the increasingly busy daily routines, individuals often feel pressured by the demands of their work and personal responsibilities. This can lead to an imbalance in maintaining commitments to church service. Perhaps, this is also a reason why many people are not interested in becoming servants in the Church.

PPC officials have a significant responsibility in maintaining this balance. They must be able to lead and inspire the congregation to remain committed to church service while managing their work and personal responsibilities. Their success in achieving this balance will have a positive impact on the Church. The involvement of PPC members, mostly laypeople, in serving the Church is interesting to explore with an analysis of work-life balance. The main focus of this research is on the balance between church service and personal work for PPC members in the Deanery of Malang City. The author will adopt the work-life balance dimensions proposed by Fisher et al. to highlight this issue.

Several previous researchers conducted their studies within the framework of work-life balance. Their studies are outlined in the following elaboration. Work-life balance and career development positively influenced employee job satisfaction (Asepta & Maruno, 2018). This research provides useful information for the company to improve employee job satisfaction.

However, this research was only conducted in one company and did not include other companies. Additionally, the study did not address other factors that could affect employee job satisfaction, such as the work environment and salary. The higher the work-life balance, the higher the job satisfaction. Conversely, the lower the work-life balance, the lower the job satisfaction. This research also showed that the work-life balance variable contributed effectively by 31.9% to the job satisfaction variable (Shabrina & Ratnaningsih, 2019). Further, personal life and work matters are two different things. They cannot be mixed, but both are on the main priority scale that must be carried out. Participants felt responsible for managing various aspects of their personal lives and completing their work matters (Wibowo & Hartono, 2020). Each aspect cannot immediately fill the shortcomings of the other because both have equal portions and occupy the main priority scale to be carried out.

The above authors successfully explained the influence of work-life balance on a person's life. Their research was mainly conducted on company employees. So, how does the analysis of work-life balance translate into the lives of church officials, especially PPC members? That is what we deepen into in this writing with the aim of contributing and determining the differences from previous researchers.

This research is based on the following research questions: Does pastoral service in the Church interfere with the personal work of PPC members in the Deanery of Malang City? Does the personal work of PPC members in the Deanery of Malang City interfere with their pastoral service in the Church? Does pastoral service in the Church enhance the quality of the personal work of PPC members in the Deanery of Malang City? Does the personal work of PPC members in the Deanery of Malang City enhance the quality of their work in the Church? Based on these research questions, it is clear that the purpose of this research is to explore the balance between pastoral service in the Church and the personal work of PPC members in the Deanery of Malang City, Diocese of Malang, in their pastoral service.

CIC 1983 can. 511 asserts that dioceses are allowed to establish a pastoral council to assist the bishop in pastoral work within the diocese. Additionally, can. 536 § 1 adds that parishes can form a pastoral council where the faithful are invited to engage in developing pastoral activities. The Parish Pastoral Council is where the laity embodies participation and responsibility in the Church's mission. It serves as a means to realize the Church's mission, as mentioned above.

The Parish Pastoral Council is a communion consisting of priests/pastors, laypeople, and religious brothers and sisters. This council is responsible for deliberating, deciding, and implementing pastoral services. The Parish Pastoral Council is called to participate in Christ's threefold mission in pastoral service. The definition of the Parish Pastoral Council varies from parish to parish or diocese to diocese, but it retains the same elements (cf. Rom 12:4-5). This is because each provides a definition according to the emphasized elements. However, the faithful understand the parish council not only through its definition but also through its role and duties (Tondowijoyo, 1990). The Parish Pastoral Council itself consists of the Daily Parish Pastoral Council, the Core Parish Pastoral Council, and the Plenary Parish Pastoral Council.

The services performed by the Parish Pastoral Council members in the church can have a significant influence on their personal work. When PPC administrators are actively involved in church service, they often have to allocate extra time and effort to organize, supervise, and participate in various church activities. This can pose challenges in maintaining a balance between church service and their personal work. Leadership in the church requires a high level of commitment and dedication, which can sometimes interfere with the time that should be used for work or other personal commitments. Nevertheless, many members of the parish council report that church service brings profound meaning to their lives and enhances leadership skills and collaborative abilities. For example, research by Batson and Ventis on church service highlights how the experience of service can shape individuals' spiritual identity and have a positive impact on their leadership development within the church community (Batson & Ventis, 1982).

The personal work carried out by the parish council members can have a significant influence on their roles and involvement in church service. Job demands that require time and commitment can limit their availability to actively engage in church service. This may result in constraints in attending church meetings, serving in various capacities, or participating in church projects that require additional time. However, conversely, the experience and skills gained through personal work can assist parish council members in management, leadership, and organization within the church context. Research by Carpenter and Ghosh on church leadership notes that personal work experience can provide valuable insights and skills in managing resources, making decisions, and designing strategies applicable in the context of church service (Puls, 2011).

The participatory-community service by the parish council creates an inclusive and community-centered church environment, where decisions and service initiatives are shaped through active participation of church members and involvement of the surrounding community. This approach is based on the concept of participatory decision-making and service aiming to understand and respond to the needs and aspirations of the church community. It creates opportunities for all church members to be involved in the decision-making process and implementation of service programs relevant to their context. Thus, participatory-community service strengthens the bond between the church and its community, creating a closer relationship and promoting more effective and relevant service to the community (Eade, 1997).

The ideal concept of service by the parish council is service based on spiritual values, loyalty to the church's teachings, and active service to the community that integrates pastoral wisdom, inclusivity, and positive impact on community life. This involves a deep understanding of the needs and aspirations of church members and their community, prioritizing service that supports spiritual, social, and community well-being. The ideal service also promotes active participation and involvement of the entire congregation in church decision-making, creating an inclusive atmosphere that appreciates diversity and facilitates spiritual growth. In this context, the parish council serves as a link between the church

community and the church itself, bridging a strong and sustainable relationship between the congregation's needs and effective church service (Groome, 1991).

The relationship between effective service and authentic leadership by the parish council is closely related and mutually reinforcing. Authentic leadership practiced by the parish council creates an environment that fosters trust, transparency, and commitment among council members and the entire congregation. In this context, authentic leaders listen empathetically, respect diverse views, and uphold moral and spiritual values. This creates a conducive climate for effective service because council members who feel supported and emotionally connected will be more motivated to actively participate in the implementation of church service. Conversely, effective service offered by the church, such as pastoral care, religious education, or social services, can help support the spiritual growth and well-being of the congregation, creating a strong foundation for authentic leadership (Maina, 2017).

Authentic leadership can also serve as an example for parish council members in organizing quality and meaningful service. When leaders demonstrate integrity, sincerity, and a strong commitment in carrying out their ecclesiastical responsibilities, it can inspire and motivate council members and the congregation to engage more deeply in service and the church's goals. Therefore, the positive relationship between authentic leadership and effective service is mutually reinforcing, creating a balanced, impactful, and spirited ecclesiastical ecosystem to fulfill the Christian calling of serving others and developing faith.

The fundamental guiding principle for PPC members in carrying out their duties and responsibilities in the church is the understanding and practice of spirituality in work (Tondowijoyo, 1990). Spirituality in work for PPC members is a concept that emphasizes the profound meaning of each task and responsibility they undertake. They see their work as a spiritual calling, not just administrative tasks. PPC members realize that church service is a concrete form of living out their faith and serving God. Every action they take, from planning liturgical activities to managing social programs, is considered an action that can bring them closer to God.

Understanding spirituality in work also involves the idea that work is not just a routine but an opportunity for contemplation and reflection on the presence of God in all aspects of service. This means that each task is seen as a moment to experience God and draw near to Him. Therefore, PPC actively seeks God in their daily activities, creating a strong connection between service and spiritual growth (Golparvar & Abedini, 2014).

Contemplation is also an integral part of spirituality in PPC's work. PPC members reflect on the meaning and purpose of their work, connecting it to the values of faith and the views of the Catholic Church. They seek guidance and inspiration from the Holy Spirit through prayer and reflection. In doing so, they ensure that every decision they make in their roles as PPC members is the result of careful spiritual discernment.

Furthermore, the concept of spirituality in work leads to an awareness of the importance of community in church service. PPC members do not work alone but as part of a larger

community of believers. They understand that the strength and success of their service depend on cooperation and brotherhood among them, as well as the support of the parish community.

Engaging in spirituality in work also creates opportunities for PPC members to practice moral and ethical values in their work. They challenge themselves to live with integrity, love, and justice in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. In implementing church service, they also strive to be role models for the parishioners in practicing the values of faith in daily life.

Through spirituality in work, PPC members make their service a form of living prayer. They recognize that their work is not just about creating effective programs but also about bringing closeness to God to the parishioners. This creates a deeper and more meaningful faith experience for both them and the parish community.

Spirituality in work also establishes a strong moral foundation for PPC members. They recognize that church service is a calling that requires dedication, commitment, and humility. They carry out their duties and responsibilities with pure intentions, reflecting on deeper meanings in every action, and always seeking spiritual growth in their work (Singhal & Chatterjee, 2006). Spirituality in work is a profound principle that guides PPC members in church service. This understanding transforms how they approach their tasks and responsibilities, directing them to see every job as a deep spiritual calling. Thus, they continue to lead the parish community in faith growth, creating service that brings love, hope, and grace to the entire church community.

Work-life balance can be defined as an individual's perception of the harmony between work and non-work activities, as well as life in general (Shabrina & Ratnaningsih, 2019). Various experts have provided definitions of work-life balance. Kalliath and Brough, as cited by Shabrina & Ratnaningsih, state that work-life balance is an individual's perception where work and non-work activities can coexist and promote personal growth according to individual life priorities. Additionally, Brough, Timms, O'Driscoll, Kalliath, Siu, Sit, and Lo describe work-life balance as an individual's subjective assessment of the harmony between work and non-work activities and life in general (Shabrina & Ratnaningsih, 2019). Thus, work-life balance is an individual's perception of the harmony between work and non-work activities and life in general.

According to Delecta, work-life balance is an individual's ability to meet the demands of both work and family commitments, as well as other responsibilities outside of work and other activities (Asepta & Maruno, 2018). This statement is supported by the definition by Susi and Jawaharrani, stating that life balance is an effort to achieve satisfaction in three basic areas of life: work, family, and personal life (Yunita, 2018). From these explanations, it can be concluded that each individual must have the ability to balance work, family, and personal life to achieve work-life balance. This aligns with Lockwood's definition, stating that work-life balance is a balanced state between two demands where an individual's work and life are equal (Mayssara, 2018).

Hudson provides additional clarification by expressing that work-life balance is the level of satisfaction or alignment between dual roles in a person's life. This definition aligns with the definition given by Greenhaus, Collins, and Shaw, stating that work-life balance is the extent to which employees are engaged and satisfied with their roles both in their work and outside of their work. From this explanation, work-life balance can also be understood as the level of satisfaction or alignment between dual roles in balancing work and non-work (Shabrina & Ratnaningsih, 2019).

According to Greenhaus, Collins, and Shaw, there are several factors that support work-life balance. These factors include: (1) Time balance: It refers to the aspect involving the amount of time given to someone for their career compared to the time given for family or aspects of life other than a career. For example, a worker, in addition to working, also needs time for vacations, gathering with friends, socializing, and spending time with family (Aseptia & Maruno, 2018); (2) Involvement balance: It refers to the psychological involvement balance in an individual's career and family. Someone with a balanced role will not experience conflicts and confusion in both areas, such as work stress; (3) Satisfaction balance: It refers to the level of satisfaction in terms of an individual's balanced satisfaction with their career and family. For example, a satisfied employee with their job at the office and satisfied with the condition of their family.

Fisher, Bulger, and Smith, as cited by Hartono and Wibowo, outline four dimensions that shape work-life balance. These dimensions are: (1) WIPL (Work Interference with Personal Life): This dimension refers to how much work can interfere with an individual's personal life. For instance, work may make it difficult for someone to manage time for their personal life; (2) PLIW (Personal Life Interference with Work): This dimension refers to how much an individual's personal life interferes with their work life. For example, if an individual has problems in their personal life, it can disrupt their performance at work; (3) PLEW (Personal Life Enhancement of Work): This dimension refers to how much an individual's personal life can enhance their performance in the workplace. For example, if an individual is happy because their personal life is enjoyable, it can make their mood at work enjoyable; (4) WEPL (Work Enhancement of Personal Life): This dimension refers to how much work can enhance the quality of an individual's personal life. For example, skills acquired at work allow an individual to utilize those skills in their daily life.

We will use the four dimensions proposed by Fisher to deepen into and elaborate on the balance between serving in the church and the personal work of the Parish Pastoral Council members in the Malang City Deanery.

METHOD

The intricate dynamics between pastoral service in the Church and the personal work of Parish Pastoral Council (Dewan Pastoral Paroki) members are explored through a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative descriptive methodology with a thorough literature study. The qualitative descriptive approach is chosen for its ability to provide a comprehensive

summary and interpretation of scholarly works on the selected topic. The research involves an extensive review of academic articles, books, and relevant sources to gain insights into the challenges and harmonization of church service and personal work among PPC members.

The chosen locations for this research are the parishes of St. Andreas Tidar and Ratu Rosari Kesatrian in the Diocese of Malang. The respondents for this study include the members of the Parish Pastoral Council (Dewan Pastoral Paroki) in both parishes, totaling 30 individuals. Data collection for this research is conducted using a questionnaire. The data analysis utilizes the quantitative method of frequency. The validation and reliability of the questionnaire are ensured by administering it to a separate group of 30 individuals who are not subjects of the research.

Thematic analysis is employed as the qualitative component of the mixed-methods design, aiming to discern recurring themes, patterns, and nuanced perspectives within the literature. The research questions guide the structured inquiry, focusing on key aspects such as the interference between pastoral service and personal work and the reciprocal impact of church service on personal work. The chosen methodology allows for a deep exploration of concepts such as work-life balance, lay participation in the Church, and pastoral ministry. Ethical considerations are paramount, focusing on accurate representation and proper citation of sources to ensure academic integrity. By synthesizing insights from the literature, this mixed-methods approach contributes to a more profound understanding of the complexities involved in balancing church service and personal work among PPC members, providing valuable knowledge for both academic and practical considerations in this context.

Table 1. Research Scheme

Variable Concept	Sub-Variables	Indicators
In this research, the term "work-life balance" is used to describe the practices of pastoral service and career. The aim of this study is to identify and support the needs of the Parish Pastoral Council (Dewan Pastoral Paroki) in achieving a balance between their pastoral service and careers.	a. Pastoral ministry interference with career life	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service and Career Energy • Family Activity Opportunities • Service and Work Pressure
	b. Career life interference with pastoral ministry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job Comfort • Work Demands • Tasks and Responsibilities • Timeliness in Service and Work
	c. Career life enhances of pastoral ministry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Service Atmosphere • Service Facts • Relationship of Goals and Functions of Service • Social Life
	d. Pastoral ministry enhances of career life	Implementing knowledge in pastoral life

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pastoral Service Significantly Disrupts the Personal Work of PPC Members

From the research findings, the author discovered that the personal work or career of the members of the Parish Pastoral Council (PPC) in the Malang City Deanery is considerably disrupted by their pastoral service in the church. In the light of *Lumen Gentium* 31, this can be

understood since the PPC members are lay believers with distinctive characteristics, namely their secular nature. They live in the world, meaning they engage in various worldly tasks and responsibilities while being part of the ordinary realities of family and social life. Their lives are intertwined with all these aspects. Their primary business is not in the context of church service but in family and social community life. They are individuals who experience ordinary life in the world: they study, work, establish friendships, engage with professionals, participate in community activities, culture, and more (Prasetya, 2021).

However, amidst the current crisis of a shortage of priests, the Church continues to encourage the involvement of the laity in pastoral activities. The call to participate in pastoral work is grounded in the awareness that the mission is carried out by the Church through all its members in various ways. Similar to the living arrangement of a body, no member is entirely passive; each one contributes to the functioning of the body. This principle applies to the body of Christ, which is the Church, where every member, according to their abilities, contributes to the growth of the body (Ephesians 4:16). This arrangement and combination of members in the body are such that those who do not contribute to the growth of the body according to their capacity are considered not useful for the Church or for themselves (Pope Paul VI, 2006). Both the laity and the clergy have the same duty to proclaim the good news, as they share the same dignity based on the common priesthood received through the sacrament of baptism (Prasetya, 2021).

For the laity, participating fully in the pastoral work of the Church is not easy due to the ongoing demands of tasks and careers necessary for their own well-being. Pastoral service in the church, which should be a source of spiritual strength, sometimes poses challenges and disturbances to the personal work of the members of the Parish Pastoral Council (PPC). In this situation, it becomes essential to emphasize "spirituality in work" or the values of the Gospel and Catholic spirituality in the career lives of PPC members. In the context of Catholic Church teachings, "spirituality in work" emphasizes the importance of integrating spiritual values into everyday work. However, when pastoral service is not aligned with this concept, dissonance can occur, affecting the balance between spiritual and professional life (Singhal & Chatterjee, 2006).

Catholic Church teachings state that spirituality should not only be part of religious rituals but should also be reflected in daily actions, including the world of work (Heuken, 2002). In this regard, ideally, pastoral service should be a means to enrich and deepen the spiritual values of PPC members, rather than a hindrance to their professional lives. "Spirituality in work" embodies harmony between the spiritual calling and career. However, if pastoral service is not integrated wisely, it can result in detrimental imbalances, exacerbated by heavy responsibilities that may create tension (Letsoin et al., 2021).

Thus, the Church needs to ensure that pastoral service not only provides spiritual guidance but also supports the deepening of moral and ethical development in the realm of career or work. The Church should continually empower PPC members to integrate spiritual

values into their decision-making and actions on a daily basis, without sacrificing their professional responsibilities (Omogo, 2019).

Personal Work Does Not Disrupt Pastoral Service for PPC Members

Through this research, the author found that the career lives of the members of the Parish Pastoral Council (PPC) in the Malang City Deanery do not actually disrupt their service in the church. This finding should be welcomed positively because, in reality, faithful believers are still willing to serve the Church amidst the careers they pursue. The PPC members present themselves as Christian believers who participate in the sacrificial spirit of Christ. Amidst the hustle and bustle of their careers, family responsibilities, and various worldly aspects of life, they are willing to sacrifice to contribute to the building of the Church as the people of God.

The involvement of the laity is acknowledged as a crucial element in ecclesiastical life. The laity is invited to actively participate in the life of the Church, both in the realm of spiritual service and in worldly duties. Therefore, there should be no sharp separation between personal work and pastoral service but a balanced integration to create a harmonious and holistic life.

Firstly, personal work can be considered a calling for the laity to feel God's calling in their daily lives. By carrying out their professional duties with integrity and dedication, members of the Parish Pastoral Council can serve as examples for the congregation. Furthermore, personal work conducted with Christian ethics can be a means to spread the values of the Church within their respective professions.

The involvement of the laity also creates awareness of the need to bring faith values into the workplace. As members of the Parish Pastoral Council, they are expected not only to play a role in the ritualistic aspects of spiritual life in the parish but also to bring the gospel spirit into the structure and culture of their work. This can be realized through ethical practices, leadership based on Christian values, and involvement in social initiatives that reflect the teachings of the Catholic Church.

In the participation of the laity, there is an opportunity to build a strong connection between personal work and pastoral service. Members of the Parish Pastoral Council can leverage their professional networks to support pastoral activities, such as organizing social events, mentoring programs, or charitable projects. Thus, personal work becomes an effective means to expand the positive impact of the Church in the community. Additionally, the involvement of the laity in the Church also provides space for the recognition that every job, regardless of its type or field, can be seen as a calling to serve others. Members of the Parish Pastoral Council can realize that their personal work is not just a source of income but also a place to provide service and create a positive impact in the world.

The laity, in the view of the Catholic Church, are Christian believers who do not belong to the ordained and consecrated ranks recognized in the Church (Pope John Paul II, 1990). The laity have duties to fulfill, namely the Triple Task of Christ as a prophet, priest, and king. Awareness of the involvement of the laity in carrying out the Triple Task of Christ should be

continually cultivated so that the laity take pride in their identity obtained through the grace of baptism.

In the context of pastoral service, the laity can play a role in prophetic tasks (proclaiming the word) by teaching religion, leading activities for the deepening of Scripture or faith, and more. In priestly tasks (sanctifying), the laity can lead prayers in community gatherings, lead choirs or singing in worship, distribute communion as extraordinary ministers, serve as altar servers, and more. In kingly tasks (serving), the laity can participate in social activities, such as providing food for the poor, healthcare services, and more. By understanding that work is also a spiritual calling, members of the Parish Pastoral Council can integrate spiritual values into every aspect of their lives, including carrying out service and work duties. *Personal Work Does Not Significantly Enhance Pastoral Service for PPC Members.*

The author found that, contrary to expectations, the career lives of the members of the Parish Pastoral Council (PPC) in the Malang City Deanery do not significantly enhance their pastoral service. The career or personal work undertaken by the members of the Parish Pastoral Council should ideally reflect the concepts of faith and the values of the social teachings of the Catholic Church. However, there are challenges in ensuring that personal work not only reflects faith but also enhances the quality of pastoral service. The concept of faith in the social teachings of the Catholic Church emphasizes that faith values should influence every aspect of life, including daily work (Pope Paul VI, 1965). Therefore, it is important to explore how faith and its influence can contribute to the improvement of the quality of pastoral service for members of the Parish Pastoral Council.

In carrying out personal work, members of the Parish Pastoral Council are expected to create a fair environment and consider common interests. However, if personal work is not conducted with justice and integrity, it can damage the credibility and moral authority of council members in carrying out pastoral service. Therefore, faith applied in daily life, especially in the context of work, can serve as a solid foundation for improving the quality of pastoral service.

The concept of solidarity in the social teachings of the Catholic Church emphasizes the importance of building supportive relationships and paying attention to the needs of others. Personal work that reflects the value of solidarity can be a means to expand the scope of pastoral service. For example, through networks and influence in their work, members of the Parish Pastoral Council can mobilize resources to support social initiatives, humanitarian projects, or broader pastoral service activities. Thus, faith experienced and applied in work can be a catalyst for broader and beneficial pastoral service.

Additionally, the concept of subsidiarity in the social teachings of the Catholic Church emphasizes the importance of entrusting responsibility to individuals or groups most suitable for specific tasks. In the context of the Parish Pastoral Council, personal work undertaken by council members can be a means to strengthen this principle of subsidiarity. They can use their influence and involvement in work to empower the parish community, motivate active participation of the congregation, and support leadership based on service. Balancing personal

work and pastoral service that reinforces subsidiarity can create a healthy dynamic in the organization of parish services.

However, if personal work is not carried out with full responsibility and awareness of faith, disharmony between work and pastoral service can occur. Lack of alignment between faith applied in work and pastoral service can harm the integrity and effectiveness of pastoral service. Therefore, it is crucial for members of the Parish Pastoral Council to actively weave this balance by integrating faith values into every aspect of life, including daily work (Wijaya & Ardijanto, 2018).

Thus, the improvement of the quality of pastoral service for members of the Parish Pastoral Council can be achieved through an understanding and application of the concepts of faith in the social teachings of the Catholic Church. Personal work that reflects the values of justice, solidarity, and subsidiarity can be a strong foundation to bridge the professional world with the spiritual calling, creating a harmonious continuity between work and pastoral service.

Pastoral Service Significantly Enhances the Personal Work of PPC Members

The author discovered that pastoral service in the Church has a positive impact on the career lives of the Parish Pastoral Council (PPC) members in the Malang City Deanery, significantly enhancing their professional lives. Profound and authentic pastoral service can act as a primary driver that improves the quality of personal work for the members of the Parish Pastoral Council, especially when linked to the concept of the influence of Catholic faith spirituality in daily work. The Catholic Church teaches that faith and spirituality should not be limited to religious activities alone but should encompass all aspects of life, including the world of work. In this context, pastoral service can be an effective channel to translate Catholic faith values into concrete actions in the professional environment of the Parish Pastoral Council members.

The influence of Catholic faith spirituality in personal work can enhance work ethics and integrity. Members of the Parish Pastoral Council, who live based on the teachings of the Catholic Church, are likely to practice moral values and Christian ethics in every decision and action in the professional world. Lived pastoral service can strengthen their commitment to truth and justice in the professional context, creating an environment that reflects faith principles (Maina, 2017).

Moreover, pastoral service enriches the meaningful dimension of the personal work of the members of the Parish Pastoral Council. By embracing Catholic faith spirituality, they can find deeper meaning in every task and responsibility they undertake. Pastoral service that involves caring for the spiritual needs of others can provide a broader perspective on the significance of daily work. For example, through pastoral service, they can find joy in making a positive contribution to others and creating a positive social impact through their work.

Pastoral service also strengthens the leadership and service capacities of the members of the Parish Pastoral Council in their professional world. In the concept of Catholic faith spirituality, a leader is expected to serve, inspire, and guide with integrity. Active pastoral

service can be real training in developing leadership based on Christian values. They can apply principles of fair management, social responsibility, and concern for the needs of others in their work context, creating a loving and supportive work environment (Spesia, 2017). The influence of Catholic faith spirituality in personal work can create a strong collaborative relationship between the members of the Parish Pastoral Council and their colleagues. Pastoral service that reflects hospitality, forgiveness, and compassion can serve as a model for interacting with others in the professional environment. This can create a positive atmosphere in the workplace, strengthen interpersonal relationships, and support the formation of an inclusive and caring community.

However, challenges may arise when trying to integrate pastoral service with personal work. There is a risk of imbalance if the focus on pastoral service becomes too dominant and compromises professional responsibilities. Therefore, members of the Parish Pastoral Council need to wisely manage their time and commitments to ensure that pastoral service does not hinder their productivity and the quality of their work. Thus, lived and integrated pastoral service with the values of Catholic faith spirituality can positively contribute to the quality of personal work for members of the Parish Pastoral Council. This creates a work environment that reflects moral values and Christian ethics, provides deeper meaning in daily work, strengthens leadership capacity, and fosters robust collaborative relationships with colleagues in the workplace.

CONCLUSION

The study found that the personal work or career lives of the PPC members are significantly affected by their pastoral service in the church. Despite being lay believers with secular responsibilities, they are actively involved in pastoral activities due to the shortage of priests. This involvement, however, can sometimes create challenges and disturbances in their personal and professional lives.

The Church encourages the laity to participate actively in pastoral work, emphasizing the unity of all members in the body of Christ. The challenge arises when this involvement disrupts the balance between spiritual life and professional responsibilities. The concept of "spirituality in work" highlights the integration of spiritual values into daily tasks, but if pastoral service is not aligned with this concept, it may cause imbalance and tension.

The Church needs to ensure that pastoral service enriches the spiritual values of PPC members without hindering their professional responsibilities. Personal work should ideally reflect Christian values and contribute positively to the community. The study also explores how faith can influence and enhance the quality of pastoral service.

Finally, while pastoral service may sometimes disrupt personal work, it is crucial for the Church to promote a harmonious integration of spirituality into both the professional and pastoral aspects of the lives of PPC members. This integration can lead to a more meaningful and balanced life, positively impacting the quality of service in both realms.

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